

Deliverable D2.1

Data Management Plan and Guidelines for FAIR outputs

Version 2

WP 2: Data technology and management for IEA
Deliverable 2.1
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1. Introduction

MISSION ATLANTIC will create new knowledge and data to assess the ecosystem status and resilience of the whole Atlantic Ocean in relation to pressures such as human activities, variability, and natural hazards. MISSION ATLANTIC follows a case study (CS) approach that includes seven regional CSs in the North, South, and Tropical Atlantic. CSs areas are nested in a basin-scale approach sharing data, knowledge, and models, to allow the quantification of: (1) the biodiversity of pelagic/benthic biomes using different metrics and their spatial distributions; (2) the climate variability; (3) the socio-ecological networks; and (4) the ecosystem-based management for integrated ecosystem assessments (IEA). The project will exploit machine-learning methods to deliver a step change in our ability to extract and process large quantities of ecosystem data, to deliver indicators, to map ocean risks, and to autonomously identify seafloor characteristics. MISSION ATLANTIC partners will make available a set of data from standard monitoring cruises, in addition to numerous future scientific and commercial trial cruises that are planned to occur during the project.

2. Data summary

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the data types and formats that will be generated during the project, the standards that will be applied, the actions for data archiving and long-term maintenance, the access and reuse policies, and the quality standards. MISSION ATLANTIC will collect and generate diverse types of data. Based on the collection method, the degree of manipulation, and their physical nature, the data have been classified into seven data types with similar data management needs: (1) environmental data, (2) biological data, (3) imaging, (4) acoustic data, (5) spatial data products, (6) modelling data, and (7) socio-economic metrics. This diversity requires an ambitious DMP, building on existing open science resources that are interoperable. The data types description and characterization (section 2.1) will be updated as data outputs crystallise from CSs and WP activities during the lifespan of the project, in order to assure a standardized data characterisation. As such, this DMP should be considered a 'living document'.

2.1 Objective of this deliverable

Deliverable D2.1 presents an initial DMP for the MISSION ATLANTIC project, under the WP2 *Data technology and management for IEA*. WP2 will implement a coordinated data management approach that operates from the start until the end of the project to ensure that data produced during the project are well documented and archived, made accessible and interoperable. WP2 has three main tasks:

- Task 2.1: Map the data availability by addressing the Integrated Ecosystem Assessment (IEA) needs (input to WP1);
- Task 2.2: Develop a cost-effective approach for data management, quality control and data access, including cost-effective solutions ensuring that project data are FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable); and
- Task 2.3: Establish technology demonstrators on big data storage and analyses, to observe and map benthic and pelagic biomes, and to fill data gaps in existing models by delivering systems supporting the blue- and bio-economy.

MISSION ATLANTIC will make optimal use of existing international infrastructures and standards to develop this data management plan and align with international efforts to support an All-Atlantic Ocean Research Community and to create an All-Atlantic Ocean Data Space. A thorough data management strategy will support the project outputs, and will ensure FAIR access to datasets and data products produced under the project. This document will be revised and updated during the project lifetime.

The primary focus of the data management plan is the data collected and data products generated in the framework of this project. However, MISSION ATLANTIC will generate other project outputs such as (i) publications and (ii) open source scripts used to generate the results and data products. We refer to these project outputs in section 2.5.

2.2 Data types

2.2.1 Environmental data

Environmental data consist of abiotic measurements from the ocean-atmosphere boundary layer (conventional meteorological observations, climatologies), the subsurface distribution of sea water properties in the water column and the sea floor. They can be collected using both *in situ* methods (water samples, buoys, sensors) and remote sensing (satellites, ocean stations). We include here physical, biogeochemical, and marine litter data. Each subtype may include the following measurements:

Physical data: Temperature, salinity, turbidity, currents, sea level, waves, air temperature, air pressure, wind speed and direction, rainfall, radiative fluxes, grab and core sediment samples.

Biogeochemical data: Oxygen, PCO₂, chlorophyll-a/fluorescence, nutrients, inorganic carbon, dissolved organic matter.

Marine litter data: Quantitative litter data present in the marine ecosystem (beach, water column and sea floor), including microplastics and collected by means of surface tows (manta trawl), sediment samples (boxcores) and organism plastic ingestion.

2.2.2 Biological data

Biological data consist of observations of species and their attributes, including biotic measurements and life-history traits. These may include measures of abundance, body size or shape, age, sex, biomass, growth and biological interactions. They can be collected from field observations (e.g., visual surveys, photo quadrats and video transects) and sample collections (e.g. trawls, nets, corers). A range of measurements can be derived from these data, such as occurrence maps, densities or abundance, species richness or diversity, genetic diversity, functional diversity, spatio-temporal species distributions and temporal population dynamics.

2.2.3 Imaging data

Imaging data comprise a collection of images (still images or videos) derived from sensors. These data will include descriptions of how sensors acquire and process the images, and information content of the images, such as qualitative and quantitative taxonomic and habitat descriptors. The data can be collected from a variety of sensors and/or instruments such as FlowCam, LOKI and vehicle platforms

(e.g., ROV, AUV, gliders). Data derived from images may include measures of occurrence, abundance, biomass, proportional area coverage, diversity, biological interactions and qualitative annotations (e.g. coral reef photo quadrats record the change in coverage and coral health).

2.2.4 Acoustic data

Acoustic data consist of both passively recorded sounds and backscattering intensity recorded by active acoustics. Passive acoustics include recording sounds from both anthropogenic (e.g., fishing vessels, drilling platforms) and biological (e.g., whales, dolphins, seals) sources. In active acoustics, transducers are used to produce sound and record backscattering intensity from a range of biological (e.g., zooplankton, fish, squid, jellyfish, etc.) and physical (e.g., seabed, density discontinuities) sources. Acoustic observations are made using a variety of instruments, such as echosounders (e.g. EK60, EK80), ADCPs, multibeam sonar, and hydrophones. A range of data can be derived from acoustic systems: bathymetry, seabed roughness and hardness, current speed, depth of thermocline, information on mid-trophic level species (2-20 cm) distribution, abundance and biomass, vessel noise, and the relative abundance of marine mammals.

2.2.5 Spatial data products

Spatial data products are derived data that include maps of a feature of interest across space and/or time. These products can include raster matrices (gridded data and images) or vector features, such as points, lines, and polygons, and can include temporal data at a broad variety of scales. Maps or spatial products are commonly produced from observations, interpolation of data, or from model outputs (both statistical and numerical). Examples of spatial data products include species distributions maps, habitat maps, seabed maps, anthropogenic activities and pressures maps (fishing, shipping, aquaculture, marine litter and pollution). Spatial data products are often the result of multiple datasets and might be associated with more than one data type.

2.2.6 Modelling data

Modelling data are output fields from numerical models that attempt to simulate aspects of the real world, based on data inputs and a framework of assumptions of how constituents interact. They can provide estimates of a wide range of physical (e.g. temperature, ocean currents, heat transport), biogeochemical (e.g. O₂, C fluxes, nutrient concentrations), biological (e.g. larval dispersal, biomass, species distributions, trophic level) and human use or bio-economic (e.g. cumulative pressures on species or ecosystems, potential fishery yields or costs) fields, frequently over time as hindcasts or future projections. Complex coupled ecosystem models (as those developed in MISSION ATLANTIC WP6 *Dynamics of ecosystem state and resources*) will integrate physical, biogeochemical, biological, and human use components at basin or global scales.

2.2.7 Socio-economic data

Socio-economic data consist of data about (1) human activities at sea, and the space and/or structures used to conduct human activities, such as fisheries data (fisheries areas, effort and commercial catches), and (2) coastal demographic or socioeconomic data (e.g., population, sewage treatment, main industries, agriculture, etc). They are useful to assess food provisioning, adaptation and vulnerability by studying population and human development, and economic conditions, amongst others. They can be collected in various ways, for example via commercial fisheries logbooks and vessel monitoring systems, or quantitative and qualitative surveys in the form of questionnaires and personal interviews.

2.3 Data formats

Given the wide range of data types, there is a great variety of data formats. We recommend adopting the data and metadata formats commonly used by the marine community for data submissions. This will enable the integration of the datasets into European International data portals, such as the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) and the future All-Atlantic Ocean Data Space. Table 1 gives an overview of the common data file types and the data formats accepted by the international repositories per data type. MISSION ATLANTIC partners should follow the recommended international repository data formats (column 3) where possible, and if not feasible, the accepted common data files formats (column 2). We recommend avoiding the use of proprietary software formats where possible. If data files are in a different format, we recommend converting the data to a more common data format and documenting the transformation method employed.

Table 1: Overview of common data files types and accepted data formats per data type.

Data type	Accepted common data files formats	Recommended international repositories data formats
Environmental data	1. Comma/tab separated values (.csv), 2. Text file (.txt)	EMODnet Chemistry and Physics: Ocean Data View (ODV) format Profiles, time series and trajectories: SeaDataNet ODV4 ASCII 3D observation data: SeaDataNet NetCDF with CF
Biological data	1. Comma/tab separated values (.csv), 2. Text file (.txt)	For EMODnet Biology ingestion: OBIS-ENV-DATA format https://obis.org/manual/dataformat/#obis-env-data
Imaging data	Digital image data: TIFF version 6 uncompressed (.tif); Digital video data: MPEG-4 (.mp4), motion JPEG 2000 (.mj2)	Euro-BiolImaging: under investigation

Acoustic data	Echosounder data: Simrad raw files (.raw,.idx,.bot) output by ER60/EK80 software used to operate EK60/EK80 echosounders. ADCP data: RD Instruments Workhorse data files, RDI ADCP format (.nnn) Multibeam data: Raw (.raw, .nwsf, .all, .pds, .xtf, .hsx) & Processed (HIPs&SIPs, .gsf, xyz, .ascii, .bag) Digital audio data (passive acoustics): Free Lossless Audio Codec (FLAC) (.flac), MPEG-1 Audio Layer 3 (.mp3) but only if created in this format, Audio Interchange File Format (AIFF) (.aif), Waveform Audio Format (WAV) (.wav)	Raw echosounder and ADCP data: Marine Data Archive (MDA) Simrad raw files (.raw,.idx,.bot) RDI ADCP format (.nnn) Processed echosounder data: ICES Acoustic data and oceanography portal: Comma-separated values (CSV) or eXtensible Mark-up Language (XML) EMODnet Bathymetry: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EMODnet csv (EMO format) 2. ASCII xyz 3. ESRI ASCII grid 4. EMODnet NetCDF 5. GeoTIFF 6. QPS SD (Fledermaus)
Spatial data products	ESRI Shapefile, Geotiff(.tif), tabular GIS attribute data, netCDF	Geospatial Data Portal: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Vector type: ESRI Shapefile; 2. Raster type: 2-dim: Geotiff, n-dim: netCDF (CF metadata convention)
Modelling data	Climate models containing geospatial data: ESRI Shapefile, Geotiff(.tif), tabular GIS attribute data, netCDF	EMODnet Ingestion/CMEMS: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Vector type: ESRI Shapefile; 2. Raster type: 2-dim: Geotiff, n-dim: netCDF (CF metadata convention) <p>The modelling output of WP6 will be hosted by Plymouth Marine Laboratory.</p>
Socio-economic data	Commercial fisheries logbooks and trawl survey (commercial catches): <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Comma/tab separated values (.csv), 2. Text file (.txt) 	EMODnet Biology ingestion: OBIS-ENV-DATA format https://obis.org/manual/dataformat/#obis-env-data EMODnet human activities: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Vector type: ESRI Shapefile; 2. Raster type: 2-dim: Geotiff, n-dim: netCDF (CF metadata convention)

2.4 Re-use of existing data

Table 2 describes the main datasets that will be re-used in MISSION ATLANTIC. A detailed meta-catalogue will be created to compile all data sources needed in WP1-7 by T2.1 (MS2.1) and we refer

to this catalogue for the most up-to-date information. In general, WP1, WP3, WP4 and WP6 will re-use existing data. WP1 will re-use a combination of existing data and data generated from other WPs. WP3 and WP4 will re-use data to generate new maps at the Atlantic basin scale. WP6 will re-use data to generate ocean physical and biogeochemistry models.

WP3 Pelagic Mapping will generate maps of biodiversity, food provision and pressures over the Atlantic Ocean based on 3D information on physical, chemical, and biological Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) over the whole water column.

- **Task 3.1** will re-use existing data (Table 2) to generate 3D maps of pelagic physical and chemical variables. Habitat maps for trophic, functional, and taxonomic groups will be produced using Continuous Plankton Recorded (CPR) data for the North Atlantic and combined with Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) data in the South Atlantic.
- **Task 3.2** will re-use existing data (Table 2) to generate maps of the main anthropogenic pressures in relation to fishing, shipping, aquaculture, and pollution (plastics from CPR surveys and river discharges).
- **Task 3.3** will re-use existing data (Table 2) to create maps of pelagic biomes.
- **Task 3.4** will re-use existing data (Table 2) to generate habitat suitability maps and Species Distributions Models (SDMs) of commercial Atlantic fish communities.

WP4 Benthic Mapping will generate new maps of seafloor characteristics, benthic communities, and Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) to enable IEAs in CS areas and at the Atlantic basin scale.

- **Task 4.2.1** will re-use existing data (Table 2) to create maps of seabed bathymetry, benthic habitat, selected VME taxa, and characteristics of benthic species assemblages.
- **Task 4.2.3** will re-use existing data (Table 2) to provide standardized baseline data of reef fish assemblages and benthic cover for all tropical oceanic islands of the South Atlantic.
- **Task 4.2.4** will re-use existing data (Table 2) to generate maps of the main anthropogenic pressures on benthic communities & VMEs due to bottom fishing, oil exploitation, seabed litter, telecommunication, scientific exploration, and seabed minerals in selected CS areas

The majority of the re-used datasets in MISSION ATLANTIC will not be large, in the order of MB. Exceptions are the acoustic data and modelling data. Acoustic EK60 datasets are in the range of 100 GB. Model outputs generated in WP6 are expected to be 150 TB in size.

Table 2: Overview of re-use of data per WP

WP/task	Datasets	Data source	Are data open access?
WP1, Case study Canary Current system	Global Ocean Chlorophyll, PP and PFT (Copernicus-Globcolour) from satellite observations: Monthly and daily interpolated (reprocessed from 1997)	https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/?option=com_csw&view=details&product_id=OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_CHL_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_009_082	Yes
	Global Ocean OSTIA Sea Surface Temperature and Sea Ice Reprocessed	https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/?option=com_csw&view=details	Yes

		ails&product_id=SST_GLO_SST_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_010_011	
	CCLME Upwelling index	http://www.ideo-cclme.ieo.es/Home/UpwellingIndex	To be specified
	Global fisheries database	https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201739	To be specified
	Global Fishing Effort	https://globalfishingwatch.org/datasets-and-code/fishing-effort/	To be specified
	Cumulative human impacts	https://knb.ecoinformatics.org/view/doi:10.5063/F1S180FS	Yes
	Precipitation from ERA5 monthly averaged data on single levels from 1979 to present	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels-monthly-means?tab=overview	Yes
WP3, Task 3.2	Quantifying the fisheries vessels density in space	https://www.preps.gov.br/web/	The product is accessible, the raw data are confidential
	Demographic data	https://ibge.gov.br/	Yes
	Main coastal economic sectors (agriculture, industry, services)	To be specified	Yes
	Atlantic tuna statistical databases	https://www.iccat.int/en/accesingdb.html	Yes
	Aquaculture production location data from PRIMROSE and Euroshell projects (Scotland, Ireland, England, France, Spain, Portugal)	PRIMROSE project partners.	Permission to use some countries' data might be needed
	AIS-based shipping vessels data by vessel types	Previous and ongoing CSIC-AZTI collaboration	Data owners sharing rules
	AIS-based fishing vessels data by fishing gears	https://globalfishingwatch.org/datasets-and-code/	Yes
	Spanish VMS data	National authorities	Permission by national authorities needed
	River discharges (flow rate) and nutrients (if available) in the Atlantic Ocean	To be specified	To be specified
WP3, Task 3.3	RRS James Clark Ross cruise JR20140922 - Atlantic Meridional Transect 24, JR303 (2014) - BODC	https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/inventories/cruise_inventory/report/15038/	Yes
	RRS James Clark Ross JR15001 - Atlantic Meridional Transect 25, JR864 (2015) - BODC	https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/inventories/cruise_inventory/report/15726/	Yes
	RRS James Clark Ross JR16001 - Atlantic Meridional Transect 26 (2016) - BODC	https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/inventories/cruise_inventory/report/16045/	Yes
	RRS James Clark Ross cruise JR18001 - Atlantic Meridional Transect 28 (2018) - BODC	https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/inventories/cruise_inventory/report/16983/	Yes
	12.5 kHz raw echosounder data collected on the Antarctic	http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3587678	Yes

	Circumnavigation Expedition during the austral summer of 2016/2017		
	Transect of the Antarctic Discovery in Nov. & Dec. 2015 - Bio-Acoustic Ships of Opportunity - CSIRO	https://portal.aodn.org.au/search?uuid=8edf509b-1481-48fd-b9c5-b95b42247f82	Yes
	ECOMAR - Ecosystem of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge at the Sub-Polar Front and Charlie Gibbs Fracture Zone (JC037)	https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/inventories/cruise_inventory/report/9459/	Yes
	Benthic-pelagic coupling cruises (JR230)	https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/inventories/cruise_inventory/report/14037/	Yes
	DISCOVERY 2010 Scotia Sea survey (JR161)	https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/inventories/cruise_inventory/report/8262/	Yes
	Oceans2025: Porcupine Abyssal Plain - Sustained Observatory (PAP-SO) (JC062)	https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/inventories/cruise_inventory/report/10589/	Yes
	National Centers for Environmental Information: Water Column Sonar Data Collection. National Centers for Environmental Information, NOAA.	https://doi.org/10.7289/V5HT2M7C	Yes
WP3, Task 3.4	Environmental values (Temperature, Salinity, Dissolved Oxygen, Nitrate) for developing SDM	WORLD OCEAN ATLAS 2018 https://www.nodc.noaa.gov/OC5/woa18/	Yes
	Environmental values (Chlorophyll, Currents) for developing SDM	CMEMS https://marine.copernicus.eu/	Yes
	Commercial fish species distributions for developing SDM	https://obis.org/ , https://www.gbif.org/	Yes
WP4, Task 4.2.1	Sediment composition maps to benthic habitat maps	https://www.marinha.mil.br/chm/dados-do-bndo/outros-dados-e-produtos	Yes
	Benthic habitat maps (Benthic)	https://www.ospar.org/work-areas/bdc/species-habitats https://www.emodnet.eu/en/seabed-habitats	Yes
	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems	https://vme.ices.dk/map.aspx	Yes
	Digital bathymetric model	https://www.marinha.mil.br/dhn/?q=en/node/249 https://www.emodnet-bathymetry.eu/ https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/mgg/bathymetry/multibeam.html http://smcbrasil.ihcantabria.com/	Yes
	Photoquadrants of the benthic community 2013-2019, in the South Brazillian Shelf (Santa Catarina state), Brazilian Oceanic Islands and Ascension and Santa Helena Islands.	Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina databases	Yes, available to non-MA partners after the end of the project.
WP4, Task 4.2.3	Visual census of reef fish 2007-2020, in the South Brazillian Shelf (Santa Catarina state), Brazilian Oceanic Islands 2013-2019, Ascension Island 2015 and Santa Helena Island 2022.	Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina databases	Yes, available to non-MA partners after the end of the project.
	Remote underwater video of reef area 2011,2013,2015 in the South	Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina databases	Yes, available to non-MA partners after the end of

	Brazilian Shelf (Santa Catarina state), Brazilian Oceanic Islands and Ascension and Santa Helena Islands.		the project.
WP4, Task 4.2.4	Oil exploration blocks maps	To be specified	Yes
	Mining areas	To be specified	Yes
	Maps of environmental sensitivity to oil	http://bibdig.biblioteca.unesp.br/handle/10/26089	Yes
	Fisheries and fisheries-related data at spatial scales	http://www.searoundus.org/	Yes
	Pressure data from different fishing industries used to assess ecosystem condition for the SA National Biodiversity Assessment	To be specified	No. Permission for use required from government department
	Shipping data used in the SA National Biodiversity Assessment	To be specified	Yes
	Aquaculture data used in the SA National Biodiversity Assessment.	To be specified	No
	River discharges and flows data used in the SA National Biodiversity Assessment.	To be specified	No
	Marine mining and offshore oil and gas data used in the SA National Biodiversity Assessment.	To be specified	No. Permission for use required from government department
	Cumulative Pressure Impact layer, used in SA National Biodiversity Assessment	To be specified	Yes
	Estimate demersal trawl intensity within the South African EEZ	To be specified	No permission to share the raw logbook data, owned by the government (Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries); Map will be made available online once it is published with DOI.
Mapping demersal assemblages from trawl survey data	To be specified	No permission to share the raw survey data, owned by the government (Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries); Map will be made available online once it is published with DOI.	
WP6	Spatially explicit estimates of stock size, structure and biomass of North Atlantic albacore tuna (<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>) in the North Atlantic for the period 1956-2010	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.830797	Yes

2.5 Other project outputs

2.5.1 Publications

Deliverable 9.1, the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEP) of MISSION ATLANTIC is ensuring that results, activities and knowledge generated in the project are effectively communicated, disseminated and transferred to end-users leading to effective exploitation for maximum

impact. Therefore, specific protocols have been developed for scientific publications, but also other communication materials such as factsheets, the MISSION ATLANTIC website, social Media, e-Newsletter and press releases. We refer to these protocols and the DEP for more details.

2.5.2 Open source code, scripts and software packages

MISSION ATLANTIC is stimulating open science practices and sharing of open source tools and scripts. Therefore, we aim to share all our open source scripts on a dedicated MISSION ATLANTIC github page: <https://github.com/missionatlantic>

We compared three major git platforms to identify the best fit for the MISSION ATLANTIC project (see Table 3 below), from which it was clear that github is the preferred platform. By using the free online github repository there is no need to set up or maintain this with IT resources. Github is the most popular platform with widespread use and is generally conceived as the best platform to share open source projects. Github has the largest community and is the best platform to generate visibility and promote the reuse of the open source scripts.

Table 3: Comparison of Git platforms terms

	Github	Gitlab	Bitbucket
Pricing - what offers the free version	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> unlimited public and private repositories unlimited number of collaborators 2,000 Actions minutes/month (500MB of storage) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> unlimited public and private repositories unlimited number of collaborators 400 CI/CD minutes/month (10 GB per repo) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> unlimited private repositories Up to 5 users 50 build minutes/month (1 GB large file storage)
Summary of reviews¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the best for open source projects and visibility + easy to use + most popular, widespread, largest community + 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> good in some specific set-ups is itself open source + slower, less popular than github - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> preferably if you are using the Atlassian Suite (Jira/bamboo) focus on (closed) enterprises - not the best user interface -
Summary of terms (see appendix 2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> users own the content they post on the platform (and are responsible for this content). The platform will of course store it somewhere to make the platform work. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> users own the content they post on the platform (and are responsible for this content). The platform will of course store it somewhere to make the platform work. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> users own the content they post on the platform (and are responsible for this content). The platform will of course store it somewhere to make the platform work.

A more elaborated summary of the terms of each git platform is summarized in Appendix 2.

A github repository template has been developed (<https://github.com/missionatlantic/MissionAtlantic-template>) but needs to be refined in collaboration with the other work packages, so that the different scripts or github repositories in MISSION ATLANTIC follow the same logical and easy to understand structure. It is up to the creator

¹ reviews consulted on 2021-05-04 (among others): https://medium.com/@Magical_Mudit/github-vs-bitbucket-vs-gitlab-1594e26d8f16, <https://stackshare.io/stackups/bitbucket-vs-github-vs-gitlab>, <https://jelvix.com/blog/bitbucket-vs-github-vs-gitlab>

of the code to document the scripts and make sure the scripts are easy to understand and follow. We recommend to use MIT software license as this is a simple permissive license with conditions only requiring preservation of copyright and license notices, which fit the open science goal of MISSION ATLANTIC.

Once the code, scripts and software packages reach a level of maturity, they can be released and archived for long-term preservation. The recommended platform to archive software is Zenodo. There is a [MISSION ATLANTIC Zenodo project](#) so any release on Zenodo can be linked to the project outputs. More detailed information about the procedure to release and archive to Zenodo will be given in the next update of the data management plan.

2.6 Data utility

Data used and produced in MISSION ATLANTIC will be useful for the assessment, modelling, and management of the whole Atlantic basin based on its ecosystem components. The IEA approach will link these components to relevant ecosystem pressures such as human activities and natural hazards. This will help to describe the current state of the Atlantic Ocean and forecast its evolution, fundamental knowledge for predicting the ocean response to environmental and climate change. Specifically, and in relation to the objectives of the project, the collection of data in MISSION ATLANTIC will be used in the following:

- The assessment of the Atlantic ecosystems status and its resilience will be useful to quantify cumulative and cross-scale impact of pressures, and consequences for food provision, climate regulation, and cultural services.
- The modelling of future 3D distributions of Atlantic biomes and their pressures will improve the sustainable use of marine resources. In addition, the broad spatio-temporal resolution of the data used and produced in the project will improve our understanding about the current status of the Atlantic biomes and their pressures at new scales of observation (e.g. global and regional, time series and seasonal).
- The ecosystem-based management procedures will contribute to the sustainable governance of marine resources and the development of the Blue Economy through dissemination of the project results, co-creation of management recommendations, and more general ocean-awareness activities involving regional stakeholders (e.g. NGOs, industry, ecosystem managers).

3. FAIR data

3.1 Making data findable, including provision for metadata

To ensure that all project-generated data are FAIR, MISSION ATLANTIC will develop an approach for data management and data access enhancement, including solutions for quality control. All metadata of the datasets created in MISSION ATLANTIC will be collected in a central metadata catalogue, the Integrated Marine Information System ([IMIS](#)), which is hosted by the Data Centre in the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ). Partners generating data will be required to provide the necessary metadata information completing the metadata form (see Annex 1), and VLIZ will collate and review the

information. Detailed steps are explained in section 4. Protocol for data management and resources (phase 1 metadata submission and phase 2 data submission).

The general archive for long term preservation of MISSION ATLANTIC data is the Marine Data Archive ([MDA](#)), which is hosted by VLIZ. Where relevant and feasible, data outputs will be visualised on a MISSION ATLANTIC GIS-platform and submitted to relevant EMODnet lots. Table 4 lists some potential data repositories for redistribution of each data type generated in Mission Atlantic.

Table 4: Potential data repositories for long-term storage and redistribution of the thematic data types.

Data type	Data repository	URLs
Environmental data	Chemical: EMODnet Chemistry Physical: EMODnet Physics	https://www.emodnet.eu/en/chemistry https://portal.emodnet-physics.eu/
Biological data	EMODnet Biology and EUROBIS (European Ocean Biogeographic Information System)	www.emodnet.eu/biology www.eurobis.org
Imaging data	Plankton images: EcoTaxa Biological (microscopy) images: Euro-BioImaging	ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/
Acoustic data	Acoustic raw data: MDA Acoustic processed data: ICES Acoustic data and oceanography portal Acoustic multibeam data: EMODnet bathymetry and NOAA National Centres for Environmental Information (NCEI)	https://mda.vliz.be/ https://www.ices.dk/data/data-portals/Pages/acoustic.aspx https://www.emodnet-bathymetry.eu/ https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/mgg/bathymetry/multibeam.html
Spatial data products	Different EMODnet lots depending on the content of the product.	
Modelling data	Climate models: to be specified	https://marine.copernicus.eu/ The modelling output of WP6 will be hosted by Plymouth Marine Laboratory.
Socio-economic data	Commercial fisheries logbook data: EMODnet Biology A product generated by commercial fisheries logbook data: EMODnet human activities	www.emodnet.eu/biology https://emodnet.eu/en/human-activities

As part of D2.1 and D9.1 Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy, mature project outputs will be issued a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). A DOI can be assigned when the metadata and data are provided and after confirmation that the dataset meets quality standards and contains all necessary metadata.

3.2 Making data openly accessible

Following the guidelines of the H2020 regulations defined for the Open Research Data pilot, all data collected or produced in MISSION ATLANTIC (including in international waters) should by default be open access and unrestricted by the end of the project. This means that data will be freely accessible at no charge to third parties and available for long term (as long as the data repository exists). Where relevant and feasible, data generated will be made accessible by deposition in the major European data portals (Table 3). In cases where the data will be accessible through these portals, a link to these systems will be included in the metadata. In cases where re-used datasets cannot be shared or they need to be shared under certain restrictions, a justification will be provided on the legal and contractual reasons in table 2 and an appropriate licence will be set. The data and metadata will therefore be available for as long as those portals are available and, as per the policy in MDA and IMIS, metadata will be available in perpetuity, together with the data, unless the data owner requires it to be removed.

The documentation instructing how to access the data are described in each of the data repositories listed in Table 3 or at the software's documentation used to access the data. The recommendations for data produced in MISSION ATLANTIC is to use open file formats that can be handled by open software (e.g. the foreseen formats to be used in MISSION ATLANTIC are specified in Table 1). Searches, visualisation, and access to spatial data products generated in the project will be facilitated via the web platform based on [Geonode](#) under D2.3. This is a state-of-the-art, open-source Spatial Data Infrastructure that will allow:

- Discovery of data products using search engine technology
- Visualisation of data products by creating and sharing interactive web maps
- Enable comments, rating and sharing of data products
- Access of data products over the web using standard Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) protocols

3.3 Making data interoperable

MISSION ATLANTIC data generators are required to follow international data and metadata standards as provided by EMODnet in order to enable interoperability with international initiatives such as the future All-Atlantic Ocean Data Space. This will facilitate data exchange and re-use of the data. To aid interoperability, international and recognized standards and controlled vocabularies will be applied to metadata and data. The use of common controlled vocabularies in the metadata and data, and the use of common data formats, are important prerequisites for consistency and interoperability, and also enable records to be interpreted by computers. MISSION ATLANTIC data generators should follow the recommended data formats per data type indicated in Table 1, and the following controlled vocabularies resources for standardisation of names:

- The [BODC Vocabularies](#), (British Oceanographic Data Centre) for parameters, units, and instruments.
- The World Register of Marine Species ([WoRMS](#)), for crucial quality control of taxonomic data, for biological data or any other type of data that includes species names. Taxonomy can be

standardized by referencing the [matching aphia id](#) from WoRMS. In this way, differences in spelling, or use of species names will be corrected.

- The [Marine regions](#), for standardized marine georeferenced place names and areas.
- When unique or uncommon ontologies or vocabularies are used by data providers, a mapping of these to more commonly used ontologies are required.

3.4 Making data re-usable

The majority of the data generated in MISSION ATLANTIC will be open access under a Creative Commons license. The type of license and terms of use for each dataset will be indicated in their metadata. The use of one of the following is highly preferred:

- **CC-0** - Public Domain Dedication, <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>
You waive any copyright you might have over the dataset and dedicate it to the public domain. You cannot be held liable for any (mis)use of the data either. You can copy, modify, distribute and perform the work, even for commercial purposes without asking permission. Although CC-0 does not legally require users of the data to cite the source, it does not take away the moral responsibility to give attribution, as is common in scientific research.
- **CC-BY** - Attribution, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>
You are free to share (copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and to adapt (remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially). You must attribute any public use of the database, or works produced from the database, in the manner specified in the license. For any use or redistribution of the database, or works produced from it, you must make clear to others the license of the database and keep intact any notices on the original database.

Open access data generated in MISSION ATLANTIC will be accessible for re-use after the life-time of the project with no plans to end provision of these data. It will therefore be available for re-use for as long as the archives exist and as soon as the protocols have been developed or the research has been completed and published. Access rights after disclosure will depend on the creative common license those data or products hold, as described earlier in this section. For the products created with restricted data, any necessary discussions with the data owners for the re-use of those datasets and or/products need to be arranged by the partner using those restricted datasets.

The initial quality control of the data during data collection is the primary responsibility of the MISSION ATLANTIC data provider. Any quality control procedures or protocols can be described in the metadata of the dataset. Before datasets are made available through the international repositories, they may need to pass a series of quality control procedures, which aim to improve data quality and completeness.

4. Protocol for data management and resources

Task 2.2 WP2 leader coordinates the process of data management during the project, while different sub-tasks are completed by different task partners. During the data collection phase, each MA partner is responsible for managing the dataset they are collecting and they must follow the data management plan. The submission workflow includes several steps to be performed by data providers and data managers (WP2). These steps consist in 2 phases:

Phase 1: Metadata submission

- Data providers submit the metadata via TEAMS. The metadata template is located in TEAMS in WP2 – Data Technology and Management > T2_2_MakeDataFair > Metadata > *Metadata_Template.xlsx* and in Annex 1. This file is a working document that contains 7 sheets, where only the 'Metadata' sheet needs to be filled. Additional sheets are used for guidance/dropdown lists.
- Data managers check the metadata is correctly filled in.
- Data managers integrate the metadata in IMIS.
- Data managers assess what the most appropriate data format is and standards for submission to the EMODnet thematic portals and inform the data submitter.

Phase 2: Data submission

- Data providers submit the datasets via TEAMS if the files do not exceed 3GB, or via their online file transfer platform of choice (e.g. ftp, Eudat B2Drop, wettransfer, web services...) if the files exceed 3GB. Additional metadata fields may be requested by data managers depending on the repository targeted.
- Data managers check the data is provided in the appropriate format.
- Data managers integrate the dataset in the Marine Data Archive (MDA).
- Data managers inform the relevant EMODnet lots or other data repositories of the intention to submit the datasets (if feasible).
- Data providers assist relevant EMODnet lots/data repositories with submitting their datasets and passing the necessary quality control steps.

Data and metadata must be submitted as soon as possible and at the latest 6 months before the end of the project, in order to complete the above steps before the end of the project.

The responsibilities of the data provider include:

- The quality control of data, during data collection, is the primary responsibility of the MISSION ATLANTIC data provider.
- Each MISSION ATLANTIC data provider must submit the data for their generated datasets in a recommended data format or accepted data file format.
- The primary responsibility for back-up and recovery of data lies with the MISSION ATLANTIC data provider; once the data are stored in the MDA, that responsibility also lies with VLIZ.

- The primary responsibility to take necessary measures to ensure data security lies with the MISSION ATLANTIC data provider. Once stored in a repository, the repository staff and managers are responsible for the protection of data and metadata that they store.

MISSION ATLANTIC will strive to be compliant with the EU regulations regarding the protection of personal data and will promote a culture of openness and sharing of data. MISSION ATLANTIC will stimulate the exchange of good practices in data access and sharing by liaising with existing European initiatives, such as EMODnet, and All-Atlantic sister projects in support of the creation of an All-Atlantic Ocean Data Space. After the project is completed, VLIZ is responsible for the long-term storage of the research outputs that are stored on the MDA, and for the publication and dissemination of data described in IMIS. Data providers are the main point of contact for questions about the dataset(s). Implementation of this DMP is necessary at the partner level. The primary responsibility of ensuring data security lies with MISSION ATLANTIC data providers. Once the data have been transferred to the MDA and/or to any international repository for long term preservation, the security of those data rests with the professional data centres that run such repositories.

MDA and IMIS are services provided by VLIZ and their costs and maintenance are covered by that organisation. Similarly, most of the European data infrastructures recommended as repositories are free of charge. Further data management costs are eligible as part of the MISSION ATLANTIC grant agreement conditions, where WP2 accounts for 11% of the total person months to perform data management and demonstrate technologies for (big) data collection, storage and analyses. Resources for a dedicated data centre to store the ca. 450 Tb of model data produced in WP6 have been allocated to Plymouth Marine Laboratory.

5. Ethical and GDPR aspects

MISSION ATLANTIC data providers are required to be compliant with the fundamental [ethical principles](#) required of all research activities carried out under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme. In addition, they need to be compliant with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) regarding the protection of personal data for any survey or questionnaire that involves the collection of personal data and not allow the transfer of personal data (e.g. email addresses) to other entities. For more information on GDPR, please consult section 3.4.4 in the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of WP9. MISSION ATLANTIC will comply with all ethics requirements and we refer to the dedicated work package WP11 Ethics Requirements in this project. The research carried out in MISSION ATLANTIC does not involve the use of genetic resources or traditional knowledge associated with genetic resources. Therefore, MISSION ATLANTIC does not fall within the scope of the EU [Access and Benefit Sharing](#) (ABS) Regulation or the Nagoya Protocol regulations (For non-European participants). If this changes during the lifetime of the project, MISSION ATLANTIC data generators must comply with the aforementioned regulations.

6. References

Horizon 2020 FAIR Data Management Plan template,
https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

7. Document Information

EU Project	No 862428	Acronym	MISSION ATLANTIC
Full Title	Towards the Sustainable Development of the Atlantic Ocean: Mapping and assessing the present and future status of Atlantic marine ecosystems under the influence of climate change and exploitation		
Project website	www.missionatlantic.eu		

Deliverable	N°	D2.1	Title	Data Management Plan and guidelines for FAIR outputs
Work Package	N°	2	Title	Data Technology and Management
Work Package Leader	Lennert Schepers, Erwann Quimbert			

Lead Beneficiary	Vlaams Instituut voor de Zee vzw (VLIZ), Partner 6			
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Version log			
Issue Date	Revision N°	Author	Change
25.01.2021	Version 0.1	Patricia Cabrera, VLIZ Lennert Schepers, VLIZ	First version, review by Jock Currie, Roland Proud, Tim Collart, Thomas Furey, Tiago Gandra, Juan Pablo Quimbayo, Dan Lear, Josean Fernandes, Erwann Quimbert and Lohengrin Fernandes
26.01.2021	Version 0.2		Second version, review by Neil Holdsworth
04.02.2021	Version 1		Final version, review by Elliot John Brown and Patrizio Mariani
23.06.2021	Version 1.1	Patricia Cabrera, VLIZ Lennert Schepers, VLIZ	This update includes (1) the addition of the metadata submission process and the metadata template in Annex, (2) the link to the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of WP9, (3) how our data management work links to the other All-Atlantic initiatives and (4) a new section on sharing scripts with github.
29.06.2021	Version 2		Final version, review by Erwann Quimbert, William Lafarge Jock Currie, Neil Holdsworth, and Juan Pablo Quimbayo.

Annex 1: Metadata template

1.1 Metadata table

Metadata field	M(andatory or O(ptional)	Description
Dataset title (English)	M	The title gives an indication of the content of the dataset; the time period and the region of sampling. It should be descriptive, meaningful and concise, allowing users to easily know what to find in the dataset.
Dataset title (original language)	O	The title as explained in the above field but in the original language (if applicable).
Abstract	M	A short summary of the dataset. This is an extension of the title addressing the following questions: WHAT, WHERE, WHEN, HOW, WHY and WHO. Character limit 1000 characters (no space).
Citation	M	The proposed dataset citation should reference the dataset, and not a paper using or describing the dataset. Therefore, the dataset title should be included in the dataset citation. VLIZ recommends the following format. Data Creator(s) Person; Data Creator(s) Institute (division); (Publication Year); Title and Identifier, Publisher.
Data creators	M	All people and/or institutes who are responsible for the creation of the dataset.
Metadata provider	M	The person that can be contacted in case there are questions related to the dataset. This is also the person who is most likely to stay involved in the dataset the longest. Name: last name(s), first name(s), Institute (Institute, department, division), email.
File name	M/O	Filename of the data submitted. Please include the extension (e.g., .zip, .csv, .xls), Mandatory if the dataset is provided. Optional if only metadata is provided.
Data type	M	Choose one (or more) data type descriptions, see section 2.2 'data types' in this document. If the dataset contains more than one data type include them separated by a comma (",").
Dataset format	M	The format in which the dataset is provided. Pick from dropdown list. If there is not a specific format, choose "Format to be defined"
Documentation	O	In cases where no common (suggested) data formats are adopted, include documentation about the formats used. Verify with WP2 if all necessary information is included.
Data origin	M	Pick from dropdown list. Refer to the sheet "Data origin" for descriptions of each field.
Data quality processing	M	General explanation about the lineage of a dataset. A statement on process history and/or overall quality of the data set. A link to a protocol or a manual of Quality Control Procedures can be added as well.
Keyword(s)	M	Different keywords that are especially important and/or descriptive for the dataset. You can either pick them from the standard ASFA list (https://vocabularyserver.com/asfa/), fill them in by yourself or combine keywords from the list and keywords entered by yourself, separated by ";".
Data license	M	Clarifying under which conditions the dataset can be used. We request the use of CC-BY (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). If this license cannot be used, please provide a reason.
Temporal coverage	M	For the dataset in YYYY-MM-DD format (or other ISO 8601 compliant formats).
Geographical coverage	M	List area(s) or location(s) where the data were collected. We advise using Marine Regions to find the adequate geo-units.
Geographical bounding box	M	(Min)Lat - (Min)Long - MaxLat - MaxLong: Western-most coordinate of the limit of the dataset extent, expressed in longitude in decimal degrees (positive east). Eastern-most coordinate of the limit of the dataset extent, expressed in longitude in decimal degrees (positive east) Northern-most coordinate of the limit of the dataset extent, expressed in latitude in decimal degrees (positive north) Southern-most coordinate of the limit of the dataset extent, expressed in latitude in decimal degrees (positive north). The geographic longitudes and latitudes must be expressed in decimal degrees, using the spatial reference system EPSG:4326 (WGS84).

Vertical extent	O	The coordinate reference systems for the expression of the vertical component in marine areas has been refined by the Elevation thematic working group of the INSPIRE annex II theme. For depth values of the sea floor in marine areas with an appreciable tidal range, depths shall be referenced to the Lowest Astronomical Tide (LAT), as has already been mandated by Technical Resolution A2.5 of the International Hydrographic Organisation (IHO). In marine areas without an appreciable tidal range, in open oceans and effectively in waters deeper than 200 metres (where tide is not measured, since it has no significant impact on the accuracy of the sounding), the Mean Sea Level (MSL) shall be used as the reference surface.
Taxonomic cover	M/O	Overview of the taxa included in the dataset. We recommend using the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) to describe internationally accepted taxonomic groups. Search here http://www.marinespecies.org/ Only mandatory for datasets that contain taxonomy. If more than one is applicable include them separated by a comma (",").
Parameters	M	The variables measured or calculated in the dataset. This includes physical, chemical, biological, geological or human activity measures. If applicable, add also the units (e.g., water temperature in Celsius, Fahrenheit or Kelvin2).
Essential Ocean Variables (EOV's)	O	Include here EOV's from GOOS listed on the third sheet. If none is applicable, leave the field blank. If more than one is applicable include them separated by a comma (",").
Sampling device	O	Free text, or can be picked from the sheet "Observing platforms" and/or from BODC sampling instruments list: http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/Q01/current/
References	O	If there are publications (or websites) based on/or describing the dataset or related datasets (e.g. preceding), it is highly recommended that they are referenced as well. A link will be made between the publications, (related) datasets, projects and websites. Please specify the relation of the reference to the dataset (e.g. paper describing the methodology, describing the dataset, using the dataset, etc).

1.2 Data origin

Data origin	Description
Monitoring: field survey	Dataset results from long term monitoring. This means monitoring over many years. It's usually organized at institute level and has a minimum duration of 4 years. Periodical sampling activities at the same location for shorter duration are considered "research: field survey".
Research: field survey	Dataset results from field research
Research: field experiment	Dataset results from a field experiment
Research: lab experiment	Dataset results from a lab research
Research: experiment	Dataset results from an experiment. In case field or lab experiment is not applicable.
Sensor platform	Dataset results measured by sensors on a fixed platform
Literature research	Dataset results from Literature research
Museum collection	Dataset based on specimens kept in a (museum) collection
Data collection	Databases generated by compiling or combining data from different data type sources. Only select this option if the dataset contains data from different data types. If the dataset is compiled from different datasets which are all from the same data type, you should select this data type.
NA	If none of the above is applicable

1.3 Dataset format

Data type	Data format
Environmental data	Ocean Data View (ODV) https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/delivery_formats/odv_format/
	SeaDataNet NetCDF with CF
	SeaDataNet ODV4 ASCII
Biological data	OBIS-ENV-DATA https://obis.org/manual/dataformat/#obis-env-data
Imaging data	Format to be defined
Acoustic data	Format to be defined
Spatial data products	Format to be defined
Modelling data	Format to be defined
Socio-economic data	Format to be defined

1.4 EOVs

Essential Ocean Variables	Type
Sea state	Physics EOVS
Ocean surface stress	Physics EOVS
Sea ice	Physics EOVS
Sea surface height	Physics EOVS
Sea surface temperature	Physics EOVS
Subsurface temperature	Physics EOVS
Surface currents	Physics EOVS
Subsurface currents	Physics EOVS
Sea surface salinity	Physics EOVS
Subsurface salinity	Physics EOVS
Ocean surface heat flux	Physics EOVS
Oxygen	Biogeochemistry EOVS
Nutrients	Biogeochemistry EOVS
Inorganic carbon	Biogeochemistry EOVS
Transient tracers	Biogeochemistry EOVS
Particulate matter	Biogeochemistry EOVS
Nitrous oxide	Biogeochemistry EOVS
Stable carbon isotopes	Biogeochemistry EOVS
Dissolved organic carbon	Biogeochemistry EOVS
Phytoplankton biomass and diversity	Biology and ecosystems EOVS
Zooplankton biomass and diversity	Biology and ecosystems EOVS
Fish abundance and distribution	Biology and ecosystems EOVS
Marine turtles, birds, mammals abundance and distribution	Biology and ecosystems EOVS
Hard coral cover and composition	Biology and ecosystems EOVS
Seagrass cover and composition	Biology and ecosystems EOVS
Macroalgal canopy cover and composition	Biology and ecosystems EOVS
Mangrove cover and composition	Biology and ecosystems EOVS
Microbe biomass and diversity	Biology and ecosystems EOVS
Benthic Invertebrates abundance and distribution	Biology and ecosystems EOVS
Ocean Colour	Cross-disciplinary EOVS
Ocean Sound	Cross-disciplinary EOVS

1.5 Observing platforms

Observing platforms
Satellites
Boundary current arrays
Argo profilers
Surface gliders
XBT and TSGs
Ship based sampling
Coastal surveys
HF radar
Ice tethered profilers
Deep Argo
Drifting buoys
Ships of opportunity
Animal CTD
Nets CPR
Mooring
Sea level gauges
Gliders
Marine meteorology
Ship based time series
Acoustic network
Particulate export flux

Annex 2: Comparison of Git platforms terms

	Github	Gitlab	Bitbucket
Link to terms (accessed on 2021-05-04)	https://docs.github.com/en/github/site-policy/github-terms-of-service	https://about.gitlab.com/terms/ (GitLab terms) https://about.gitlab.com/terms/signature_all.html (gitlab.com terms)	https://www.atlassian.com/legal/cloud-terms-of-service https://www.atlassian.com/legal/product-specific-terms#bitbucket-cloud-specific-terms
Ownership	Users own the content they post on GitHub. However, users have some responsibilities regarding it, and Github asks to grant us some rights so we can provide services to you.	We do not claim any ownership rights to the information that you submit to the GitLab application itself, your code is yours. (gitlab.com terms) 5.8 Customer represents and warrants that it has, and shall retain, all right, title and interest (including, without limitation, sole ownership of) relating to Customer Content, and the intellectual property rights related thereto. (GitLab terms)	5.1. Using Your Data to provide Cloud Products to You. You retain all right, title and interest in and to Your Data in the form submitted to the Cloud Products.
Rights granted to service	right to store, archive, parse, and display Your Content, and make incidental copies, as necessary to provide the Service, including improving the Service over time This license does not grant GitHub the right to sell Your Content.	GitLab shall be responsible for establishing and maintaining a commercially reasonable information security program that is designed to: (i) ensure the security and confidentiality of the Customer Content; (ii) protect against any anticipated threats or hazards to the security or integrity of the Customer Content; (iii) protect against unauthorized access to, or use of, the Customer Content; and (iv) ensure that all subcontractors of GitLab, if any, comply with all of the foregoing.	Subject to these Terms, and solely to the extent necessary to provide the Cloud Products to you, you grant us a worldwide, limited term license to access, use, process, copy, distribute, perform, export, and display Your Data. Solely to the extent that reformatting Your Data for display in a Cloud Product constitutes a modification or derivative work, the foregoing license also includes the right to make modifications and derivative works. We may also access your accounts, End User Accounts, and your Cloud Products with End User permission in order to respond to your support requests.
Rights to other users	If you set your pages and repositories to be viewed publicly, you grant each User of GitHub a nonexclusive, worldwide license to use, display, and perform Your Content through the GitHub Service and to reproduce Your Content solely on GitHub as permitted through GitHub's functionality (for example, through forking). You may grant further rights if you adopt a license.	?	If you are accessing code in someone else's repository, you should carefully read all the licenses applicable to that repository before using or contributing any code. YOU ACKNOWLEDGE THAT ALL CODE MADE AVAILABLE THROUGH BITBUCKET CLOUD IS THE RESPONSIBILITY OF THE ACCOUNT OWNER CONTROLLING THE PARTICULAR REPOSITORY. WE ARE NOT THE LICENSOR OF ANY THIRD PARTY CODE MADE AVAILABLE THROUGH BITBUCKET CLOUD AND TAKE NO RESPONSIBILITY FOR SUCH CODE.
Cancelling and account deletion	Upon account cancellation we will delete your full profile and the Content of your repositories within 90 days of cancellation or termination (though some information may remain in encrypted backups) We will not delete Content that you have contributed to other Users' repositories or that other Users have forked.	?	?

<p>Service termination</p>	<p>GitHub has the right to suspend or terminate your access to all or any part of the Website at any time, with or without cause, with or without notice, effective immediately. GitHub reserves the right to refuse service to anyone for any reason at any time.</p>	<p>GitLab reserves the right to suspend service to the SaaS Software if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Customer fails to comply with the Agreement and this Appendix, (ii) Customer exceeds set application limits, or (iii) requests or usage deemed malicious in nature is identified to be sourced from Customer accounts, personnel, or systems. 	<p>Since Bitbucket Cloud is designed to be used as a source code repository, we reserve the right to remove any other content (such as music or video), particularly if the content is consuming a disproportionate amount of storage. Please note that, since we do not maintain access to your repositories, any removal of Your Data under Section 5.5 (Removals and Suspension) of the Agreement means removal of the entire repository in which the offending data resides, not just the offending portions.</p> <p>We may offer certain Cloud Products (including some Atlassian Apps) to you at no charge, including free accounts, trial use and Beta Versions as defined below (collectively, “No-Charge Products”).</p> <p>We may modify or terminate your right to use No-Charge Products at any time and for any reason in our sole discretion, without liability to you. You understand that any pre-release and beta Cloud Products, and any pre-release and beta features within generally available Cloud Products, that we make available (collectively, “Beta Versions”) are still under development, may be inoperable or incomplete and are likely to contain more errors and bugs than generally available Cloud Products.</p>
<p>Backups</p>	<p>Github enterprise has some tools to create a backup: https://github.com/github/backup-utils</p>	<p>GitLab will architect and maintain an underlying cloud infrastructure with commercially reasonable resiliency for all data, compute, and network services. At a minimum, GitLab will maintain the highest documented level of “GitLab Reference Architecture” as detailed at https://docs.gitlab.com</p> <p>GitLab will maintain a commercially reasonable system of data backup process and technology to ensure that primary data sources remain recoverable in the event of various system failures.</p>	<p>?</p>